

PREVALENCE OF OVARIAN CYST AND ITS ASSOCIATED FACTORS AMONG PATIENTS VISITING MARDAN MEDICAL COMPLEX: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Ovarian cysts are a common gynecological issue that affects women worldwide. Most ovarian cysts are benign and asymptomatic, impacting about 7 to 18 percent of women at some point in their lives. Objective: Prevalence and associated factors of ovarian cysts among patients visiting Mardan Medical Complex. Methodology: A total of 337 patients with ovarian cysts participated. Height, weight, and BMI were measured using standard protocols. Results: Total of 177376 visits, and 337 of them obtained a diagnosis of ovarian cysts, which gives a period prevalence of 1.89 patients per 1000 population. Ovarian cysts appeared to be common in patients having irregular menstrual cycles ($p=0.009$), contraceptive use ($p=0.001$), and insertion of IUDs ($p=0.012$). Cysts increased, as expected, with fertility treatments ($p=0.001$), but shrank with pregnancy ($p=0.001$). There was a higher incidence of hemorrhagic cysts in those with endometriosis who had undergone pelvic surgery ($p=0.001$). On the other hand, dermoid (3.6%) and chocolate cysts (3%) were rare, whereas simple cysts (45.1%) and hemorrhagic cysts (36.7%) were the most common types of the ovaries. Conclusions: A low prevalence of ovarian cysts at 1.89%, exhibiting variations in size and type. Irregular menstrual cycles, contraceptive use, and fertility treatments heightened risk, whereas pregnancy facilitated cyst reduction. Hemorrhagic cysts were prevalent in endometriosis and post-surgical cases, while simple cysts were the most common. Most cysts were not dangerous, but those that were bleeding needed more attention.

INTRODUCTION

One set of small, almond-shaped organs at the bottom of the female pelvic cavity, are the ovaries; one is on each side of the uterus. They are important components to the female reproductive system, and are involved with both reproduction and hormonal regulation (1). On average, each ovary is about 2 to 4 centimeters in size, however, size can vary based on age,

hormone levels and whether or not a woman is pregnant. The ovaries are connected structurally to the uterus by the ovarian ligament, and receive their blood supply from the ovarian arteries (2).

The ovaries have two primary functions: The synergy of egg production (oogenesis) and

hormone secretion, e.g., estrogen and progesterone, occurred by this mechanism (2).

The ovaries are divided into two distinct regions: the outer cortex and the inner medulla. Developing follicles are present at different stages of maturation in the cortex and connective tissue, blood vessels, nerves, and lymphatic vessels in the medulla (3).

The functional anatomy of the ovaries revolves around two primary processes: folliculogenesis, that results in the release of an egg (ovulation), or steroidogenesis, the production of hormones such as estrogen and progesterone. They are intimate with the

menstrual cycle and are extremely important for fertility, as well as for women's overall health (4). The follicle supports the oocyte (immature egg) by nourishing its inner surface, which is inside the follicle, with its surrounding granulosa cells whose presence generates estrogen in response to FSH. Estrogen levels that rise increase the endometrial lining in the uterus, thickening it for possible implantation should a fertilization occur (5).

Just prior to ovulation, luteinizing hormone (LH) surges during the middle of the menstrual cycle. In ovulation the mature follicle bursts releasing the oocyte into the fallopian tube to be fertilized by sperm (6). If fertilization does not occur, the corpus luteum degenerates into the corpus albicans, a scar like structure, and progesterone levels decreases. When the progesterone goes down, that causes the breakdown of the lining of the uterus and causes menstruation (7). These processes are disrupted to cause ovarian cysts. An example is a follicular cyst, where a follicle doesn't rupture and release the egg, resulting in fluid build up within the follicle. (5,8).

Ovarian cysts can be caused by hormonal imbalances or by disruption of normal ovarian physiology. Cysts normally arise from follicles or corpus lutea which are expected to work incorrectly during the menstrual cycle. There are two types of cyst that are most commonly linked to hormonal imbalances these are **follicular cysts** and **corpus luteum cysts**, which are usually benign (9,10). Additionally, **polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)** can cause the growth of multiple ovarian cysts. The cause of PCOS is raised levels of androgens (male hormones) which disrupt normal ovary function causing the

development of many small cysts on the surface of the ovary (11).

The most important diagnostic tool for the detection and assessment of ovarian cysts is ultrasound imaging because it is non-invasive, very accurate and allows for real time visualization of ovarian structures. **Transvaginal ultrasound** is the preferred method of imaging the ovaries because it gives closer proximity to the organs and better clearer and more detailed images (12).

Ultrasound is particularly accurate in diagnosing ovarian cysts, especially those simple, fluid filled cysts, such as follicular cysts or corpus luteum cysts, which are thin walled, anechoic (dark) 'structures' on the scan. While **dermoid cysts** are often more complex in structure because of their varying tissue contents (hair, teeth, bone), they can be seen as echogenic (bright) areas on ultrasound. **Endometriomas** also tend to have a specific 'ground glass' appearance on ultrasound, due to the thick, blood-filled contents of the cyst (12,13) A major advantage of ultrasound is its ability to differentiate benign from potentially malignant cysts. Most ovarian cysts are benign, but some may be larger, have a solid component, or look different, and need to be evaluated further, because they may be ovarian cancer (14).

Objectives and Rationale:

The main objective of this research is to find out the prevalence of ovarian cysts among the female patients coming to Mardan Medical Complex. The secondary objectives are to determine how demographic characteristics, such as age, reproductive history, and family medical history, influence the risk of having ovarian cysts.

The study aims to identify correlations between these factors and the risk for ovarian cyst development to understand the etiology of such cysts in the local area population. The research can help improve various diagnostic protocols and improve patient care using a possible evaluation of the detection rates and patterns of ovarian cysts via ultrasound.

Methodology:

The study carried out is simple descriptive cross-sectional study, this sort of study aims for deciding to determine the prevalence of ovarian cysts and its associated factors (risk factors)

among patients visiting Mardan Medical Complex. The hospital has 700 beds and is the largest healthcare facility in the northern area of KPK. The hospital aims to provide healthcare facilities to its patients, medical reforms, and physicians, training, nursing staff and allied health workers in medicine and surgery. Verbal consent has been taken off from each and every individual, and also from the hospital radiology department.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age of 18-70 years.
- Patient with history of PCOs.
- Pregnant patients.
- Unmarried women Postmenopausal women.

Exclusion Criteria:

- History of ovarian surgery: Total abdominal hysterectomy.
- Functional cyst.

Sample Size:

The sample size for this study is 337, with a confidence level of 95% which is calculated through the OpenEpi tool.

Sampling Technique:

Sampling technique used in this study was non probability, convenience sampling technique.

Data collection:

First of all, approval was taken from the Institutional Research Committee of MCMTBKMC. Before starting to collect data, an ethical approval was requested from the Ethical Committee of hospital as well as verbal consent from each participant. The designed questionnaire was given to each participant prior ultrasound examination and explained every question in a simple way to everyone. Ultrasound machine equipped with linear-array transducer (7.50 Megahertz) and convex-array (3.50 Megahertz) transducers was used for the assessment of subjects.

Statistical analysis:

Data analysis was carried out through SPSS (Statistical Package of Social Sciences) version 22, Descriptive statistical analysis (Mean, Standard deviation, frequency and percentages)

were used for description of basic factors that is age, gender, BMI, weight, height, occupation, marital status and education status. Fisher's exact test was used to correlates the ovarian cysts and its associated factors. Analysis was summarized in graphical, tabular and charts form.

Results:

In this study there were 337 subjects. The study sample has an average age of 30.7 ± 8.9 years. The sizes of cysts in the patients vary with an average size of 10.3 ± 5.7 cm, suggesting a notable dispersion of cyst sizes around the mean, indicating significant variability in cyst sizes among the patients.

In terms of marital status, 26.1% of participants, or 88 individuals, were single, while the majority, 73.9% or 249 individuals, were married. Regarding educational attainment, 48.7% of participants, equating to 164 individuals, were literate, whereas 51.3%, or 173 individuals. Occupationally, the predominant group consisted of housewives, totaling 226 participants (67.1%), followed by 47 participants (13.9%) who were employed and 64 participants (19.0%) who were students.

The average BMI is 25.9 ± 4.2 , suggesting that the participants generally fall within the overweight range classification, which indicates a moderate level of variability in BMI. The average weight recorded is 68.8 ± 13.1 kg, reflecting a diverse range of weights among the subjects. The mean height is reported as 5.7 ± 3.3 feet, indicating considerable variability in height within the sample.

The research identified substantial correlations between ovarian cyst classifications and various factors. Irregular menstrual cycles were significantly associated with cystogenesis ($P = 0.009$), especially hemorrhagic and simple cysts. Not using IUDs ($P = 0.012$) and taking fertility drugs ($P = 0.001$) were both linked to a higher rate of cysts. Pregnancy exhibited a significant correlation ($P = 0.001$), with hemorrhagic cysts being more prevalent in pregnant women and simple cysts in non-pregnant women. There was a strong link between pelvic surgery and endometriosis ($P = 0.001$). Conversely, menstrual flow ($P = 0.201$), exercise ($P = 0.634$), obesity ($P = 0.180$), diet ($P = 0.108$), medical treatment ($P = 0.547$), and family history ($P =$

0.139) exhibited no significant correlation with cystogenesis. As show in table 1.

Table 1: Association of ovarian cyst with its associated factors

Variables		Types of Ovarian Cyst n					P-value
		Follicular	hemorrhagic	Chocolate	Dermoid	Simple	
History of menstrual cycle	Regular	19	26	0	3	59	0.009
	Irregular	29	98	1	9	93	
Amount of menstrual cycle	Normal	16	25	0	2	53	0.201
	Scant	14	44	0	5	60	
	Heavy	18	55	1	5	39	
IUD use	Yes	5	16	0	3	6	0.012
	No	43	108	1	9	146	
Oral contraceptive use	Yes	20	61	0	9	42	0.001
	No	28	63	1	3	110	
Daily Exercise	Yes	6	15	0	1	27	0.634
	No	42	109	1	11	125	
Obesity status	Yes	12	38	0	5	31	0.180
	No	36	86	1	7	121	
Typical diet	High caloric	3	27	0	2	32	0.108
	Balanced diet	45	97	1	10	120	
PCOS	Yes	10	8	0	0	11	0.044
	No	38	116	1	12	141	
Pregnancy	Yes	35	90	0	9	74	0.001
	No	13	34	1	3	78	
Fertility drugs	Yes	27	54	0	7	43	0.001
	No	21	70	1	5	109	
Medication or treatment	Yes	43	114	1	11	144	0.547
	No	5	10	0	1	8	
Family history	Yes	3	15	1	0	16	0.139
	No	45	109	0	12	136	
Pelvic surgery or endometrioses	Yes	2	19	0	0	4	0.001
	No	46	105	1	12	148	

IUD: Intra uterine device, PCOS: Poly cystic ovarian syndrome

Table 2: Association of ovarian cysts with clinical features

Variables		Types of ovarian cysts, n						p-value
		Follicular	Hemorrhagic	Chocolate	Dermoid	Simple	%	
Clinical features	Incidental	2	3	0	1	3	2.7	0.001
	Abdominal and pelvic pain	23	50	0	8	65	43.3	
	Menorrhagia	2	3	1	0	2	2.4	
	Swelling	2	6	0	1	5	4.2	

Irregular cycle	8	45	0	0	41	27.9
Lower back pain	10	16	0	2	36	19
Other	1	1	0	0	0	0.6

n: frequency, %: percentage

Table 2 shows a significant correlation between ovarian cyst types and clinical features (P = 0.001). Abdominal and pelvic pain were the most common symptoms, mainly associated with simple cysts (43.3%). Irregular menses were significantly linked to hemorrhagic cysts (27.9%), while lower back pain was also frequent with simple cysts (19%). Degenerative cystic follicles were rare and mostly incidental (2.7%). The provided graph illustrates the prevalence of different ovarian cyst types within a sample of

337 cases. The simple cyst emerges as the most prevalent, constituting 45.1% (152 cases) of the total, followed by hemorrhagic cysts at 36.8% (124 cases). Follicular cysts account for 14.2% (48 cases), while dermoid and chocolate cysts are less common, representing 3.6% (12 cases) and 3% (1 case), respectively. This distribution indicates that simple and hemorrhagic cysts are the most frequently observed types.

Figure 1: Types of ovarian cyst in percentage

The study conducted over three months period (11th September, 2024 to 24th November, 2024) at Mardan Medical Complex (MMC), a total of 177,376 individuals visited the facility, of which 337 were diagnosed with ovarian cysts. The prevalence of ovarian cysts was calculated by dividing the number of individuals with the disease (337) by the total number of visitors (177,376) and multiplying by 100, resulting in a prevalence rate of 0.189%. This indicates that approximately period prevalence of 1.89 patients per 1000 population visiting MMC during this period had ovarian cysts, providing insights into the occurrence of this condition within the examined population.

Discussion:

Our study, which was carried out at the Mardan Medical Complex (MMC) in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, offers important new information about the associated factors and prevalence of ovarian cysts using ultrasonography. It found that 337 women with ovarian cyst diagnoses had a period prevalence of 1.89 patients per 1000 population. This result is at odds with a number of national and international studies that show greater prevalence statistics.

According to one study conducted in Peshawar, between 6.6% and 7% of women in their reproductive years have ovarian cysts. This suggests that our sample may be more specific or less symptomatic than larger cohorts. Furthermore, according to another study from Lahore, benign ovarian cysts make up around 90% of ovarian tumors. This is consistent with our findings that the most prevalent types of ovarian cysts are simple cysts (45.1%) and hemorrhagic cysts (36.8%). The low prevalence rate in our study, however, begs the question of whether there may be underdiagnosis or disparities in healthcare awareness and access among KPK populations.

Furthermore, our study highlights how menstrual irregularities and the use of contraceptives affect the formation of cysts, which is consistent with research showing these factors to be important contributors to ovarian health problems. Although earlier research revealed that the percentage of malignant changes linked to ovarian cysts ranged from 18% to 27%, our main focus was on benign cysts and how to treat them. This emphasizes how important it is to continue monitoring and educating people about the possible risks connected to various cyst forms.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that the formation of ovarian cysts is affected by various factors, including irregular menstrual cycles ($p=0.009$), the use of contraceptives such as intrauterine devices ($p=0.012$) and oral contraceptives ($p=0.001$), and fertility treatments ($p=0.001$). Pregnancy ($p=0.001$) associated with hemorrhagic cyst. Furthermore, there is an association between pelvic surgery or endometriosis ($p=0.001$) with the development of hemorrhagic cysts. The research underscores the prevalence of simple cysts (45.1%) and hemorrhagic cysts (36.8%), with simple cysts being the most frequently observed, while less common types include follicular (14.2%), dermoid (3.6%) and chocolate cysts (3%). The results highlight the necessity for a more comprehensive understanding of the hormonal, reproductive, and lifestyle factors that influence cyst formation, as well as the significance of monitoring more complex cysts. The prevalence of ovarian cysts within the studied was

determined to be 0.189%, providing valuable insights for future research and healthcare approaches.

Recommendation:

Recommend regular pelvic ultrasound scans for women struggling with irregular menstrual cycles. Encourage programs that help people keep their weight at a healthy level to lower their metabolic risk factors. Conduct more comprehensive, multicenter studies to learn more about the hormonal and lifestyle factors that cause ovarian cysts. Improve health education programs for women of childbearing age about menstrual health and getting medical care on time.

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